

Research Data Infrastructures Before They Were Cool: Microfilms, Photocopies and Early Digital Storage Devices in Humanities Scholarship (1950-1990)

Anna-Maria Sichani, University of London

Introduction and methodological framework: media-aware historiography of Humanities disciplines

Humanities disciplines, such as History and Philology, have historically developed methods, tools, and infrastructures for organizing, accessing, and referencing primary sources as research data. However, their historical narratives - often rooted in a print-based culture - frequently overlook the role of media and technology. However, over the past fifteen years, interest in older technological and communication media has surged, fueled by cultural "technostalgia" (van der Heijden, 2015) and a shift in Media History scholarship, flagged by the emergence of "media archaeology" (Huhtamo & Parikka, 2011; Parikka, 2012) and the contributions of media historians like Lisa Gitelman (2014) and Matthew Kirschenbaum (2016), who emphasize the material, cultural, and social dimensions of media technologies.

In that vein, concepts and practices related to research data infrastructures in historicophilological disciplines have been significantly shaped by various media technologies over the years. These technologies have, in turn, influenced and enhanced key research practices, standards, and processes, such as copying, storage, documentation, sharing, and access, that continue to be central - but not entirely new - to today's digital research agenda. However, many recent initiatives developing and establishing 'best practices' in research data infrastructures in Humanities (Gooch and Strange, 2023), especially when dealing with cultural heritage assets (Benardou et al., 2017), have overlooked the historical foundations and contributions of these infrastructures "before they were cool," failing to situate these research practices within a broader historical continuum.

This presentation summarizes preliminary findings from an interdisciplinary research on the (pre)history and use of research data infrastructures in the Humanities. This work forms part of a broader international research project currently under development for submission for international funding. The project seeks to connect and compare case studies from the UK, the Netherlands, France, and Greece, exploring the transnational and transmedia histories of media technologies like microfilming, photocopying, and early digital storage (e.g., floppy discs, CDs), within the historiographies of historical and philological disciplines. By examining these media technologies, the study highlights the overlooked material dimensions shaping historicophilological disciplines in post-war Europe while introducing a broader critical framework for examining the relationship between epistemological and methodological practices in the Humanities and their ties to historicity, materiality, media, and technology. By following Gerben Zaagma's recent work around the genealogy of Digital History through the role of technology in historical research (Zaagma 2024), this work also aims to enrich transnational historiographical accounts of the Humanities by integrating Media History and Media Archaeology. For this presentation, I will explore the case study of the introduction of microphotography in Greece, particularly in Modern Greek History and Philology after the 1950s.

A (brief) history of microphotography in Humanities research

Microphotography, a technique using microfilm to reproduce entire texts in miniature form, dates back to the mid-19th century. Introduced by the British optometrist John Benjamin Dancer, the "father of microphotography," who created the first microphotographs of texts in 1839 using a microscope and camera, the technique was further refined in 1859 by René Dagron who patented a method replacing the daguerreotype with the collodion wet plate technique, enabling clearer images and multiple reproductions (Luther 1959). Commercial interest surged in the late 1920s when Eastman Kodak released the first microphotographic plates. The development of microphotography in America advanced rapidly during the 1930s, driven by innovations like the portable camera from Recordak Corporation, which initially served banks and insurance companies before gaining adoption by libraries and research institutions, mainly for document preservation, particularly for newspapers printed on fragile wood-pulp paper and manuscripts (Binkley, 1929; Kuhlman, 1935). Key milestones included a 1936 Carnegie-funded study confirming the stability of microphotography (Binkley, 1936), the formation of the American Library Association (ALA)'s Committee on Photographic Reproduction of Library Materials (Raney, 1937), and the launch of *The Journal of Documentary Reproduction* in 1938. In subsequent years, libraries expanded the range of microphotographed materials to include newspapers, periodicals, rare books, manuscripts, and maps. Microfilm classification systems were also introduced, integrating microfilms into library collections under the principle of "treat microfilm like a book," with detailed classification information such as numbers, physical descriptions, content, and ownership/user details.

In Europe, microphotography saw extensive use during World War II for espionage and document preservation under the threat of destruction. In the post-war period, the widespread adoption of various microphotographic formats (microfilm, microfiche, aperture cards), along with advancements in photographic and reading devices, gradually expanded to England, France, and Germany (London Symposium 1949). By the 1960s, microphotography had become a widespread, cost-effective, compact and stable solution for storing the exponentially growing volume of archival and original research and archival documents. Advances in technology further cemented its role in providing efficient storage and fast and high-quality access for textual research data.

Microphotography and Modern Greek Historical Disciplines

Microphotography arrived in Greece in the early 1960s in the fields of archival and historical research, and coincided with the development of the Center for Modern Greek Research at the Royal Research Foundation under the direction and guidance of K. Dimaras. "Every time I returned from a trip abroad," noted Dimaras, "I would bring back, each time, bags full of microfilms of manuscripts or printed materials" (Dimaras 1977a), and indeed he was the one who brought microfilms in his suitcases while introducing the technique and the uses of microphotography to the historical and philological disciplines and to research processes.

Through and around this Center, and mainly through the development of newly funded Greek Enlightenment Study Group (OMED) in 1962, Dimaras promoted a series of methodological renewal attempts for Modern Greek Historicophilological disciplines by seeking "good tools for doing our job": "Organization of documentation, indexes, computerization, all media technologies are beginning to be employed to facilitate young researchers in accessing quicker their sources" (Dimaras 1969).

Since the 1960s Dimaras initiated more than hundred scientific missions for microphotography and cataloging documents, manuscripts and printed archival assets across Greek monasteries, libraries and special collections, establishing also the Microfilm Archive (Sklavenitis 1982). Microfilms from these missions as well as special orders from abroad were stored at the Archive, with on-site reading machines available for researchers. Microphotography quickly became an infrastructural technology for Greek researchers, granting them access to otherwise inaccessible historical resources, while introducing the concept of affordable, mechanical copy and (re)use of research data for multiple cases/uses. Researchers gained access to research data without the need to travel to the source institutions, transforming their research and working conditions long before the advent of the

digitization revolution. Microfilms were further enhanced with detailed documentation and finding aids, including reference numbers, which streamlined their search, retrieval, and referencing; they quickly became an integral part of the Center's library holdings, prioritizing access over the broader goal of preservation of archival and historical resources (fig.1-2).

These microfilm collections have been pivotal in enabling groundbreaking research outputs from dissertations, scholarly editions of rare material, editions of correspondence and large scale bibliographies and indexes of journals. These outputs, particularly in the fields of Modern Greek Enlightenment and Early Modern Greek Studies, have profoundly shaped the development of disciplines of History and Philology in Greece over the past 70 years. Microfilms also introduced innovative solutions for data management, such as compiling complete journal series by combining microfilms from multiple libraries ("composite journal bodies") (Dimaras 1967). Additionally, the introduction of new formats like microfiche in the 1970s revolutionized access, availability, and portability of research data (Dimaras 1977b).

Fig.1-2. Microfilms stored at the storage units of the Center for Modern Greek Research

The Historical and Paleographic Archive (IPA) of the Educational Foundation of the National Bank of Greece also started its microphotographic collection in 1975, with the stated goal of preserving and microfilming historical archives and manuscript codices in Greece (IPA 1978, 8). Since its inception, IPA employed microphotography both to preserve and to provide access to historical source materials through scientific missions across Greece, while systematically organizing expert research services centered around microfilms as accessible research data infrastructures. These services extended across media and technologies, including offering photocopies derived from microphotographs and providing microfilm copies, relying to expensive machines for this task (reel-

to-reel), as well as the option to borrow microfilms for a minimal fee, while providing formal ways to referencing the microfilms as sources, while encouraging national and international collaboration across institutions (fig.3-4). Finally, around the microfilm collection, IPA developed an informed, technologically-supported institutional expertise around Paleography and Textual Studies, with specialised publications, annual seminars and classes around paleography and preservation of primary documentary sources, following the example of the Center for the History of Texts of the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)” (Tselikas 1994).

Fig. 3. The HIRAKAWA camera for microphotography at IPA

Fig. 4. The MICROPRINT KODAK machine at IPA, for producing photocopies from microfilms.

Conclusion

The above brief overview of the adoption and use of microphotography by the historical and philological research community in post-war Greece allows us to discern the progressive change in working conditions as well as the epistemological and methodological development of the fields of Modern Greek History and Philology. Interestingly, while microfilms globally addressed the issue of storing growing volumes of newspapers and books, in Greece, microphotography initially served as a tool for accessing hard-to-reach archival documents. The Greek library sector massively adopted microphotography only in 1984, starting with the microfilms of the daily press collections at the

Library of the Parliament. Furthermore, microfilm introduces the concept and practice of the accessible copy into the workflow of Modern Greek historical and literary fields, thus inaugurating a series of practices around the relationship of researchers with the original source and its technically mediated reproductions, visible to this day in the digital environment, resulting to new protocols of research practices around possession, storage, sharing, access, and (re)use of research data. Not surprisingly, modern copyright legislation has been shaped around the concepts of reproduction and copying, with rights for use and distribution of copies first being formalized in relation to microfilms; in Greece, a systematic legal framework for copyright was established only in 1993. Finally, microfilm, which allowed limited interventions in copies, was quickly replaced by commercial photocopiers in research environments. These media technologies, easy to use and affordable, enabled a wide range of user interventions, fundamentally altering the way we process and use copies and research data.

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